

Proposal: Cultural Heritage Information Package

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Created: 25 September 2024

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1 - Background:

Over the past decades, data scientists, cultural heritage professionals, and digital humanities scholars have laid the foundation for a robust cultural heritage cloud by leveraging web semantics and ontology-driven approaches. Core technologies such as RDF (Resource Description Framework) and OWL (Web Ontology Language) have been instrumental in enabling the Linked Open Data (LOD) paradigm, ensuring that cultural heritage data is semantically rich, interoperable, and machine-readable across platforms. Ontologies like Dublin Core and CIDOC-CRM serve as essential frameworks for structuring metadata, offering a standardized approach to describe, contextualize, and interlink cultural heritage assets. Furthermore, community-driven principles such as FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics) ensure that this data is not only technically interoperable but also ethically sound and socially inclusive. These principles support the equitable sharing and responsible reuse of cultural heritage data, fostering openness, collaboration, and broader accessibility within the global cultural heritage ecosystem.

Significant infrastructures like Europeana, DARIAH, and AriadnePlus have played vital roles in enabling large-scale cultural heritage research. Europeana serves as a digital platform for sharing and accessing millions of cultural heritage items, DARIAH supports the digital humanities by fostering collaboration and offering tools and services for research, and AriadnePlus provides a research infrastructure for archaeological datasets. End user tools have emerged such as ResearchSpace, Geovistory and the Archaeological Interaction Report, offering collaborative environments for semantic data management and knowledge discovery. Other lightweight digital tools such as Peripleo and Recogito facilitate the visualization, annotation, and spatial mapping of historical data. Researcher-driven consortiums such as Pelagios Commons focus on building community-driven initiatives to link and explore historical resources through open data practices. By fostering interdisciplinary research and collaboration across the cultural heritage sector, these infrastructures, tools, and networks together form a web of interconnected cultural heritage knowledge, supporting deeper scholarly engagement with historical data.

These building blocks are reaching a level of maturity and interoperability that enables a transformative next step in the organization of the cultural heritage cloud. This next step can reposition the cloud, formalizing the relationship between, on the one hand, cultural heritage knowledge and, on the other hand, repositories of digitized items with their metadata. This will evolve the cloud into a dynamic record of human interaction with cultural heritage objects. Such a repositioning allows us to not only preserve items but also to capture and document the concerns, activities, and scholarly engagements associated with these objects over time.

To further this aim, I propose a structured and reusable information product: the Cultural Heritage Information Package (CHIP). The CHIP builds upon the groundwork outlined above,

offering a framework that formally records concern for cultural heritage objects as discrete modes of human engagement—such as permission, research proposal, research report, conservation, and education— and pairs that with an annotated bibliography that contextualizes the concern. By doing so, it adds a new layer of information valence, transforming the cultural heritage cloud into an evolving space that captures both the heritage item and the complex scholarly and cultural concerns surrounding it.

The CHIP concept builds directly on the advances outlined above, offering a flexible, standards-based framework that addresses the growing need for more integrated, interoperable cultural heritage data. By adhering to FAIR principles, the CHIP system ensures that cultural heritage data is easily discoverable, accessible through open protocols, interoperable with existing standards, and reusable in multiple scholarly and organizational contexts.

CHIPs, by design, are autonomous and unregulated. This highly desirable feature of the CHIP concept exposes a serious potential weakness: knowledge fragmentation. Our proposal recognizes this and responds by articulating an additional core concept: Curated CHIPs.

The CHIP concept thus addresses a key concern expressed in the [Report on a European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage](#): the need for “a really strongly integrated complex including the design of novel integrated activities in the digital continuum, together with a trend towards a digital ecosystem including all concerned actors and stakeholders.” This need is addressed by providing a flexible and scalable solution for documenting human concern across the continuum of cultural heritage activity. The federated CHIPer Grid aligns with the report's emphasis on collaboration and interoperability, enabling diverse institutions to contribute and share data while ensuring semantic consistency through dynamic metadata standards. Moreover, CHIPs fully implement FAIR principles and support Linked Open Data (LOD), ensuring data is findable, accessible, and reusable, which is essential for long-term cultural heritage preservation and research.

2 - The Cultural Heritage Information Package (CHIP):

A Cultural Heritage Information Package (CHIP, Figure One) is an information product that expresses a cultural heritage concern (permission, research, publication, conservation, education) with reference to a cultural heritage item (or items) and is contextualized by an annotated bibliography. A CHIP is thus a standalone information product that can be evaluated or reviewed, reused or extended, and serve as building blocks for aggregate CHIPS. CHIPs build on the cultural heritage cloud's storage of cultural heritage items and linked metadata, adding the concepts of concern for and knowledge about cultural heritage items. The CHIP represents the fusion of four distinct information components:

1. A concern for some number of cultural heritage items (archaeological sites or historic landscapes, monuments, individual or collections of artifacts, archival documents and so forth). The use of the term concern is meant both to emphasize the commitment to care for cultural heritage but also to place each CHIP in a continuum of cultural heritage practice. This placement within the continuum thus establishes a framework within which cultural heritage professionals can collaborate and integrate workflows.
2. A semantically-structured narrative, one that bridges the gap, on the one hand, between vast quantities of complex data and, on the other hand, pure textual narratives. This semantically structured narrative is both human readable, rich with interpretative conclusions, and also machine readable, allowing, for example, viewing tools to pull data or media from remote data stores and present it in specialized viewer plugins.
3. An annotated bibliography of citations that support both the methods used in the research and interpretations of the research findings. The purpose of the annotated bibliography is two-fold. First, to bring additional academic rigor to the report and the rationale for specific citations and, secondly, to provide inputs to an AI-enabled citation curation process that results in curated annotated bibliographies.
4. Links out to authoritative representations of the cultural heritage items of concern as well as the bibliographic citations.

Clear Text & Searchable	Signed, Encrypted, Secured
Author(s) CHIP Type Referenced CH item(s)* Bibliography Cited* Creation Date Modification Date	Semantically Structured Narrative Annotated Bibliography Data Referenced* Maps Referenced* GIS Layers Referenced* Media Referenced* CHIPs Referenced*
Standardized Metadata	Extensible Metadata
* = External Links	

Figure One: The CHIP

3 - Cultural Heritage Concern:

A first requirement for a CHIP is concern for a cultural heritage item or items. The use of the term concern is meant to convey deep engagement founded on awareness that preservation of and elaboration on cultural heritage is of enduring value to society.

Cultural heritage concerns naturally organize into a flow of engagement (e.g. the social life of things) and each concern is a discrete mode of engagement. A concern is a bounded activity, with a definite start and end, and as such may produce new knowledge about the cultural heritage item(s) of concern. Categories of concern interrelate to other, public, processes within cultural heritage management and academic research (e.g., granting of permission, peer review and publication of research).

Each concern / mode of engagement has a specified set of required and optional properties. These are either datatype properties (defining the CHIP) or object properties linking the CHIP to referents (cultural heritage items, citations, data sets, other CHIPs).

4 - Annotated Bibliography:

A second requirement for a CHIP is annotations to bibliographic citations. A CHIP itself does not create or contain citations but instead, similar to the cultural heritage item itself, simply references the citation. The CHIP instead holds the annotations that provide context for and underpin the rationale for the concern. The annotated bibliography is a departure from present citation practices which sometimes can produce large numbers of citations with unclear argumentative relevance. The requirement of an annotated bibliography thus strengthens citation practices and builds a richer information space which then serves as the foundation for additional concerns.

Of course, one form of concern for cultural heritage items (or items) is research in the form of an annotated bibliography itself. When the annotated bibliography is packaged as a CHIP, it can then partake of the other services within the CHIPer Grid (see below).

5 - CHIPer Grid:

5.1 - The CHIPer Grid (Figure is a federated and resilient network designed to facilitate the management, sharing, and preservation of cultural heritage information through Cultural Heritage Information Packages (CHIPs). At its core, the CHIPer Grid is built on a distributed architecture of lightweight CHIP Servers (CHIPers), which can be easily deployed by institutions, organizations, or individuals to serve their own CHIPs. These CHIPers can either function as standalone servers that host and serve CHIPs or be configured as CHIP Nodes. When a CHIPer is flagged as a CHIP Node, it not only hosts CHIPs but also actively participates in managing CHIP address resolution, CHIP redundancy and the creation of Curated CHIPs. The CHIPer Grid directly supports the FAIR and LOD principles by creating a federated network of CHIP Nodes that store and serve cultural heritage data through open standards.

5.2 - Each CHIP Node functions as a resolver, enabling it to look up and route requests for CHIPs across the grid. When a new CHIPer is deployed, it announces itself to a nearby CHIP Node, which completes the registration by assigning the CHIPer a unique Name Assigning Authority Number (NAAN). The CHIP Node shares this information across the network, synchronizing with other CHIP Nodes to ensure the new CHIPer is recognized as a part of the federated architecture.

5.3 - CHIP Nodes also participate in CHIP redundancy. Once registered, a CHIPer establishes an ongoing relationship with its registrar Node and the latter becomes responsible for storing a copy of every CHIP retrieved from that CHIPer. The CHIPer remains independent, with the registrar Node acting solely as a redundancy partner rather than a controller of the CHIPer's data. Additionally, each CHIP Node establishes a partner relationship with a second Node and then synchronizes CHIPs with their partner. This process of registration, duplication and synchronization creates three copies of each CHIP. Finally, each Node implements an adaptive caching mechanism that stores high demand CHIPs, improving performance across the network.

5.4 - Each CHIPer will function as an endpoint (e.g. SPARQL, GeoSPARQL), enabling external systems to query its stored CHIPs and their metadata. This allows CHIPers to be part of a broader Linked Open Data ecosystem, where they can respond to queries from external tools, institutions, or users. This enables seamless interoperability between CHIPers and external

systems, allowing researchers or other CHIP Nodes to query and access information directly from the CHIPer without needing additional interfaces or custom solutions.

5.6 - One of the key strengths of the CHIP Grid architecture is its cost-effectiveness and minimal need for central coordination. Each CHIPer is independently responsible for its own CHIPs and synchronizes with its registrar Node only when necessary, reducing the burden on any central authority. The distributed resolution system means that access to CHIPs remains decentralized, scalable, and highly resilient. CHIPers can be set up with minimal technical overhead and expense while Nodes require additional investments in storage, computer power and bandwidth.

5.7 - The architecture is also designed to be adaptive to changes in the global technology landscape. As the CHIP Grid uses open standards and interoperable protocols like ARKs and federated synchronization, it can easily integrate with future technologies or platforms. The ARK model ensures that CHIPs remain accessible and resolvable even if hosting infrastructure evolves or changes. By avoiding reliance on proprietary systems or centralized services, the CHIP Grid can adapt to new tools, data formats, or networking protocols as they emerge, making it future-proof in a rapidly evolving digital world.

6 - Curated CHIPs:

6.1 - As noted above, knowledge fragmentation is a key challenge for the collaborative cloud for cultural heritage. Correlated with the expansion of the internet and the value it creates, fragmentation of knowledge and the diminution of the perceived value of expertise have emerged as problems with profound impacts on human society. We address this problem with the concept of the Curated CHIP (Figure Three).

Figure Three: CHIP Curation and Human Expertise

6.2 - Because CHIPs include an annotated bibliography they create the opportunity for integrating cross-CHIP annotations for a given citation, in effect building a curated citation. In turn, these curated citations can then be embedded in a Curated CHIP. We believe this is where Artificial intelligence has the capacity to integrate the rich diversity of human concerns and engagement represented in individual CHIPs. Additionally, and directly here addressing one of the two subject areas of the funding call, artificial intelligence can be used to, on demand, create subject-specific annotated bibliographies based on canvassing Curated CHIPs.

6.3 - Thus CHIP Nodes have an additional important role: running background processes that build curated CHIPs. These processes will leverage AI models specifically developed to integrate citation annotations. These curated citations will maintain links to the original CHIPs and their associated concern. The CHIP Node will use metrics drawn from query / request metadata to assess and select presenting areas of concern and cultural heritage items of particular interest. Based on that selection, the Node will build a Curated CHIP, incorporating its integrated annotations and relevant links to cultural heritage items and CHIPs that have expressed concern for them. The same techniques used in background processes can be run on demand to create a user-specific annotated bibliography.

6.4 - CHIPer Nodes will build the curated CHIPs by performing federated queries across the CHIPer Grid to find CHIPs with common elements, such as shared citations, cultural heritage items, or similar concerns. By sending a distributed query (e.g., SPARQL, GeoSPARQL) across the federated grid, the system collects and integrates metadata about the CHIPs that share these common elements.

6.5 - Curated CHIPs aggregate human concern and knowledge and thereby offer a robust accelerant to research. CHIP authoring tools will be designed to look for and further integrate Curated CHIPs into a personal research space. This research space serves as a foundational platform for expressing a new concern and CHIP authoring.

7 - The Role of Human Expertise:

Massive numbers of CHIPs and AI-produced curated CHIPs do not easily or directly address the socio-cultural need for human expertise. The CHIP concept needs a precise and distinct role and process for signaling CHIP quality. Fortunately, the academic community already has these in the form of peer review. Presently, peer review centers on journal publications and to a lesser degree on edited volumes. In a future where knowledge production is embedded in CHIPs, peer review can also occur for individual CHIPs (e.g., an excavation report or pre-print of excavation findings) or a curated CHIP. We see an opportunity for academic special interest groups (SIG) to coalesce around CHIP production and provide open peer review processes that contextualize the CHIP within the broader SIG expertise.

This vision for signaling CHIP quality aligns well with current trends in open science and community-driven knowledge sharing. Peer review within communities of practice emphasizes collaborative validation and evaluation of CHIPs, making this an organic extension of scholarly work.

8 - CHIP Authenticity:

Enabling a dispersed knowledge system requires ensuring authenticity of the CHIPs. To facilitate this, the CHIPer will allow authors to generate a public-private key pair when they register. The private key is used by the author to sign their CHIPs, ensuring that the content is verified as coming directly from them and has not been altered. This private key is kept securely by the author and is never shared publicly.

Each CHIP will then contain both a hashed portion and an unhashed portion. The hashed portion includes the content of the CHIP, which is signed by the author using their private key. The unhashed portion contains the author's public key, the hash signature, and clear text for searching, allowing anyone to find relevant CHIPs and easily verify their authenticity and integrity.

9 - CHIP Production and Consumption: Research Canvas and Authoring Tools

9.1 - The CHIP authoring system (Figure Three) is designed to be a flexible, web-based tool that combines a Research Canvas and an Authoring Interface, enabling researchers to access and read multiple CHIPs in their canvas as well as easily author a CHIP. The CHIP authoring tools are meant to be simple yet robust. Simplicity here equates to have a clear 1:1 relationship

between a type of CHIP and a simple authoring experience. Robustness equates to common functionality across authoring tools that ensure that appropriate metadata is captured and citation quality is maintained.

9.2 - Each type of CHIP represents a unique form of human engagement with a cultural heritage item, and as such, must adhere to specific metadata requirements that reflect the nature of the concern. These metadata standards are based on a dynamic schema system, allowing the CHIPer to retrieve the latest versions of metadata requirements as they evolve over time. We envision CHIP metadata standards being managed in a community of practice context similar to how the International Council of Museums (ICOM) manages CIDOC-CRM through its CIDOC (International Committee for Documentation). These schemas are stored centrally in a repository (e.g., GitHub), allowing the system to remain flexible without manual updates to the authoring tools. This dynamic approach to metadata management means that the system can evolve to meet the needs of various concerns while still ensuring the integrity and accuracy of the data.

9.3 - At the heart of the CHIP authoring process is the CHIPer (CHIP server), which serves as the backbone for managing metadata standards, citation acquisition, and storage. The CHIPer automatically retrieves the correct metadata schema for each concern when an author begins to create a new CHIP.

9.4 - In the CHIP authoring tools, a query language will be implemented (e.g., SPARQL, GeoSPARQL) and used to find and reference citations, cultural heritage items, and other CHIPs. Authors will be able to issue queries against endpoints, returning metadata about these items and their PID, allowing the author to include the returned item as referents in their CHIP.

9.5 - The CHIP authoring tool is designed to provide a consistent, intuitive experience for authors while adapting to the specific needs of each concern. Although the look and feel of the authoring tool remains common across all concerns, the underlying data collection fields are dynamically generated based on the concern's metadata schema. At the same time, the tool ensures that common functions—such as citation management, annotations, and validation—are handled uniformly across all concerns, ensuring a streamlined workflow that minimizes user confusion and maximizes efficiency.

9.6 - A critical aspect of the CHIP system is its ability to integrate authoritative citations into the authoring process. Ensuring the consistency and comparability of citations across all CHIPs is essential for maintaining the system's integrity, especially when aggregating annotations from different authors. To achieve this, the CHIP system will use authoritative sources for citations (e.g., CrossRef for journal article citations and OCLC's WorldCat for books). Authors will be allowed to pull their citations from personal tools (e.g., Zotero) and reconciliation to the authoritative source will be semi-automated. In cases where a citation match cannot be found, the CHIPer Grid will store the citation with a unique ID, creating a CHIPer Grid authoritative source. By eliminating the possibility of manually entered or inconsistent citations, the tool ensures that all references are traceable to their authoritative origins, further enhancing the system's overall integrity and reliability.

9.7 - The ability to handle organization-specific metadata templates adds another layer of flexibility to the CHIP system. For example, permission-granting organizations may require specialized metadata fields that extend or refine the general CHIP metadata standard. In such cases, these organizations can define their own metadata templates, which the CHIP authoring tool can dynamically acquire via a URL connection. This allows authors to easily comply with specific institutional requirements without deviating from the core CHIP metadata standards, enabling the system to cater to a broad range of scholarly and organizational needs.

9.8 - Ultimately, the CHIP authoring tool offers a powerful and adaptable framework for documenting human engagement with cultural heritage items. By ensuring that metadata schemas are dynamically managed and citation consistency is strictly enforced through authoritative sources, the system provides a robust platform for creating, annotating, and aggregating CHIPs. Whether addressing concerns of research, conservation, or education, the tool remains flexible and easy to use, while ensuring that the resulting CHIPs are rigorously structured and fully interoperable across the broader cultural heritage community.

10 - A Use Case: Field and Lab Research Findings CHIP:

The Fieldwork and Lab Research Preliminary Report CHIPs will focus on providing a semi-automatic way to summarize field or lab research into preliminary reports, published under appropriate country-specific guidelines, into the CHIPer Grid. This CHIP type leverages AI to semi-automatically compile, structure, and link research data into a comprehensive preliminary report. These reports will draw from structured data, such as spreadsheets and databases, as well as non-structured data like images, 3D models, and GIS maps, ensuring that all key research outputs are referenced dynamically. The end products of the workflow are: a CIDOC-CRM based triple-store repository of the research data; a semantically-structured (i.e. not purely textual narrative) research report; the publication of a Cultural Heritage Information Package (see below) to the appropriate (ECHOES-compliant) repository; knowledge graphs based on report connections.

The process begins by ingesting structured data (e.g., CSV files) that may or may not explicitly link to corresponding non-structured data sources. AI-driven tools are employed to automatically extract data concepts and relationships between them, mapping these to a standards-based ontology (e.g., CIDOC-CRM). This ensures that all data is well-organized and interoperable, following standards for field and lab research documentation.

Once the data is organized, the AI proceeds to analyze and link these structured and unstructured data. For instance, images are linked to their corresponding artifacts in the database, 3D models are associated with their discovery locations, and GIS maps are referenced to visualize excavation sites. The AI also can be used to analyse unstructured data (e.g., images, GIS maps, 3D models) and provide annotations that further help tag and structure these items. The outcome is a preliminary findings CHIP that integrates all these data types while allowing users to interact with each dataset dynamically through a CHIP viewer.

By leveraging a “person in the process” model, researchers can interact at key points in a largely AI-driven process to ensure that field and lab data is correctly mapping to the target ontology, structuring queries that bring out specific aspects of the research findings, and ensuring the AI-built narrative accurately reflects both the raw findings and the preliminary interpretations. The resulting CHIP is lightweight as it embeds no memory-intensive objects but also semantically very rich because of links to original data, but also the list of predefined queries that showcase specific aspects of the broader data set.

The CHIP Viewer, acting as a personal research canvas, provides researchers with a rich, interactive environment. The viewer allows users to click on references in the report to visualize the corresponding 3D models, GIS maps, or other linked multimedia elements in real-time. This dynamic interaction with the preliminary report fosters a more in-depth understanding of the research findings, offering users the ability to explore both the report and its referenced data. Furthermore, the viewer integrates into the broader CHIP research and authoring environment, allowing researchers to annotate CHIPs for their personal research and easily integrate those annotations into their own authoring processes.

This interactive approach not only accelerates the creation of preliminary research reports but also ensures that field and lab data remain well-organized, accessible, and linked with broader scholarly contexts. Through the integration of advanced AI, the CHIP system reduces the manual workload involved in preparing reports, allowing researchers to focus more on enriching their reports with deeper analyses of their findings as well as annotating citations that support the methods, findings and conclusions in the report. The result is a comprehensive, dynamic report that can be easily reviewed, extended, or reused by other scholars, while adhering to the necessary legal and professional guidelines for research publication.

In summary, the Field and Lab Research Findings CHIP transforms the process of documenting preliminary findings by automating the integration of structured and unstructured data, and enabling real-time interaction with diverse data sets through a sophisticated viewer. The system ensures that all findings are referenced properly, dynamically linked to relevant research outputs, and embedded within the context of cultural heritage standards and community practices (e.g., CIDOC-CRM and FAIR), making this CHIP type an essential tool for researchers working in diverse, data-rich environments.

11 - Key Challenges for the CHIP Concept:

Managing Metadata Standards: One of the most critical challenges for the CHIP system is the ongoing management of metadata standards. Since the CHIP concept relies on accurate, up-to-date metadata schemas for different modes of engagement (e.g., research, conservation, education), maintaining the integrity and consistency of these standards will be crucial. Ensuring community participation and establishing clear governance processes for managing updates to these standards is essential for ensuring long-term sustainability and preventing fragmentation in the metadata that underpins CHIPs.

Technical Challenges of Federated Systems: The federated nature of the CHIPer Grid introduces several technical challenges related to network synchronization, redundancy management, and node interoperability. Since CHIPers are deployed independently and can operate as standalone servers or nodes, ensuring consistent synchronization across the grid is critical for maintaining data integrity. The architecture requires robust protocols to handle network failures, ensure that redundant copies of CHIPs are properly synchronized, and manage the registration of new CHIPers. Additionally, the challenge of maintaining low-latency access to CHIPs while balancing redundancy and caching will require careful design, especially as the volume of CHIPs grows. Handling scalability in terms of the number of CHIPs, as well as their geographic distribution across nodes, will necessarily rely on the same internet used by other services.

Ensuring Interoperability with External Systems: Another challenge involves ensuring that CHIPs remain interoperable with external cultural heritage systems and repositories. Since CHIPs reference external data (such as cultural heritage items stored in institutional repositories or linked data systems), maintaining long-term interoperability with these external sources requires careful consideration and appropriate design choices.

Ensuring the accuracy and completeness of the AI-driven processes used to generate the Field and Lab Research Findings CHIP is another challenge. While structured data can be reliably processed and linked to the preliminary report, free-text interpretation, and the mapping of complex relationships between data points (such as artifacts, images, and GIS coordinates) can vary in accuracy. AI models must be trained specifically for these domain contexts, and while most automated processes perform well with structured data, handling nuances in free-text descriptions or interpreting ambiguous links between diverse data types may require human oversight to ensure quality. Achieving seamless integration of these diverse datasets into the preliminary report CHIP requires continuous refinement of AI tools and occasional manual intervention to guarantee the correctness of the outputs. We address this problem by developing extensions to existing standards that field projects can use to define their data. [Is there scope here to build field research tools??]

Another challenge arises from the dynamic and interactive nature of the CHIP viewer. While the viewer allows researchers to explore datasets and media objects dynamically, ensuring smooth performance, especially when loading memory-intensive files like 3D models and high-resolution images, can be technically complex. The need to reference rather than embed these files keeps the CHIP lightweight but introduces dependencies on external storage and real-time rendering capabilities.

[Reflecting comments from Gethin] A final challenge for the CHIP Concept is adoption. Will small institutes be able to stand up a CHIPer? Will they need to, or can they participate in other CHIPers? Is there some critical mass such that, until that mass is achieved, the CHIP concept does not provide value? Finally, what is the risk that the concept simply does not achieve that critical mass?

12 - Possible Extensions to the CHIP Concept:

- 1) The curated CHIP concept can be extended to support being “seeded” by a selection of academic papers, links to semantic resources and CHIPs. AI tools could query bibliographic databases to find publications with relationships to the seed information.
- 2) The CHIP concept is based upon full, open access but could be extended to include secured access to a CHIP.
- 3) The use case for field reports can be extended to analog archives as well as digital archives, in which case the solution has to include AI tools to interrogate digitized analog documents.

13 - Connecting the CHIP Concept to the ECHOES Architecture:

Figure Four illustrates how the CHIP concept relates to the conceptual architecture described in the [Report on a European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage](#). Overall, the services (browser-based and server-side) described above all fall under the general category of “App” in the conceptual architecture. The exceptions to this are the CHIPs and Curated CHIPs themselves, as these are in fact “Data”.

14 - CHIPer Grid Technologies (possible)

OS: Linux

SPARQL/GeoSPARQL and RDF Support:

- Apache Jena (Fuseki) for RDF and SPARQL/GeoSPARQL querying.
- Virtuoso for a highly scalable and performant alternative.

Routing and Request Fulfillment:

- Libp2p for decentralized routing and request management using DHT.

Redundancy and Synchronization:

- Syncting for real-time decentralized synchronization of CHIPs between nodes.

Caching:

- Varnish Cache for efficient caching of popular CHIPs at various nodes.

ARK Management:

- Noid for managing ARK-based persistent identifiers.

Encryption and Signing:

- GnuPG for encrypting and signing CHiPs.
- TLS for securing communication between nodes.

Research Canvas and CHiP Authoring:

- ResearchSpace, Geovistory and the Archaeological Interactive Report - these tools have aspects of Research Canvas and Authoring, but do not specifically work with CHiPs and also do not have the citation and annotation capabilities needed. The likely solution draws heavily from them but is different in end result.

AI-Enabled Field/lab Report:

This is likely more coding from scratch but with access to libraries (depending on language, here probably Python). These libraries are quite low-level relative to the average archaeologists / archaeological scientists computing skills and hence a lot of abstraction and simplification would be required. The model would be that CHiPs are in a triple store but the data mapped in by AI would be in a backend that had other uses (direct query, website hosting), for example, Arches or Omeka-S (both could be configured)

Key libraries/platforms are:

Data Ingestion & Processing: Pandas, Apache Tika, OpenCV, GDAL.

Ontology Mapping & Standards: RDFLib, Karma, Protégé.

AI-driven Extraction & Linking: SpaCy, Stanford NLP, Neo4j.

Viewer & Annotation Tools: Three.js, Leaflet, Annotorious.

Supervision & Interaction: Jupyter Notebooks, Dash.

15 - External Links

AriadnePlus: <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Archaeological Interactive Report:

<https://portal.research.lu.se/en/projects/archaeological-interactive-report>

CARE Principles: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

CIDOC-CRM: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

CrossRef: <https://www.crossref.org/>

DARIAH: <https://www.dariah.eu/>

Dublin Core: <https://dublincore.org/specifications/>

ECHOES Architecture (European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage): <https://www.eechoes.eu/>

Europeana: <https://www.europeana.eu/>

FAIR Principles: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Federated Queries (General concept): https://www.w3.org/wiki/Federated_SPARQL_query

GeoSPARQL: <https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/geosparql>

Geovistory: <https://geovistory.com/>

Linked Open Data (LOD): <https://www.w3.org/standards/semanticweb/data>

OCLC's WorldCat: <https://www.worldcat.org/>

OWL (Web Ontology Language): <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

Pelagios Commons: <https://commons.pelagios.org/>

Public-Private Key Encryption: https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public-key_cryptography

RDF (Resource Description Framework): <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

ResearchSpace: <https://www.researchspace.org/>

SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language): <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>

The Social Life of Things:

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/social-life-of-things/6BD8EC5F4BD5735108C57873866AA92A>

Zotero: <https://www.zotero.org/>

15 - Acknowledgements

George Bruseker (<https://www.takin.solutions/>) offered a critique that strengthened the focus on semantically-structured narratives.

16 - Revision History

25 September 2024 - Created

4 October 2024 - added further weaknesses in argument

12 October 2024 - added reference to how CHIPer Grid supports SKGs

16 October 2024 - added comments in reflection of additional reading of the "Report"

20 October 2024 - added diagrams, clarified some text

Last Update - 21 October 2024 - added some thoughts on possible technology components